

Resilience: The Lifeline to Healthy Adolescence

Anil Kumar¹, Saloni Bhatti^{2*}, Kanika S. Madan³

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¹ Principal; Delhi Public School, R K Puram, New Delhi, Delhi, India; principal@dpsrkp.net

² School Counsellor; Delhi Public School, R K Puram, New Delhi, Delhi, India; salonibhatti@dpsrkp.net

³ School Counsellor; Delhi Public School, R K Puram, New Delhi, Delhi, India; kanikasmadan@dpsrkp.net

* **Correspondence:** salonibhatti@dpsrkp.net

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Abstract

The current study examines the role of resilience, a life skill, in fostering positive mental health among adolescents and supporting their holistic development. Using qualitative research methods, this study explores how resilience develops in adolescents by analysing secondary data from academic articles, psychological studies, and case reports. This study explores how adolescents, as they grow up, can develop both healthy and unhealthy perspectives about themselves, others, and the world around them. It takes into account their life experiences and how they deal with adverse situations. It emphasises how an individual and their interactions with the environment, primarily family, can influence one another in developing resilience, with reference to Urie Bronfenbrenner's systems theory, or bioecological model (1979, revised 1994). By identifying key social and psychological factors that enhance resilience, the current study underscores its importance in promoting social competence, emotional regulation and overall well-being, thereby emphasising the vital role of resilience acting as a protective factor in adolescent psychological development.

Keywords: Adolescent; Urie Bronfenbrenner Systems Theory; Resilience; Life Skills; Mental Health; Holistic Development.

1. Introduction

Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood, where teenagers need to cultivate essential skills which become a guiding factor in forming their values, attitudes, and perspective, while navigating societal and cultural influences, enabling them to effectively apply their knowledge and skills to evolve themselves into responsible, mature and healthy individuals who can learn, express themselves confidently and adapt effectively to changing life circumstances.

As adolescents face many challenging situations in their lives, such as academic concerns, changes in friendships, peer pressure, issues with friends and family, parental discord, concerns with authorities, and career-related issues, how one copes with these challenges and adversities determines one's overall well-being and quality of life. This evolution impacts adolescents' lives across various domains, including physical, social-emotional, cognitive, academic, and career domains. Thus, empowering adolescents with the necessary life skills will enable them to cope with various challenges, optimise their potential, and live happy, satisfying lives. Therefore, emphasising the ability to handle adverse situations, or resilience, helps them navigate their lives more effectively.

Resilience, therefore, helps one bounce back from or cope with stressful situations, regulate one's emotions, and serve as a buffer against challenging situations, thereby preserving one's socio-emotional and mental health. Research in the area of resilience has further shown that it acts as a protective factor against mental health concerns such as anxiety, depression, etc. Studies have found that individuals with high resilience are better equipped to cope with life's adversities than those who lack it, indicating the significant role of resilience as a life skill for ensuring one's mental health and well-being. In addition, it has emphasised that an individual's characteristics and support from friends, family, school, and society at large play a crucial role in strengthening resilience.

1.1. Research Objectives

The specific objectives of this study are:

1. To examine the role of resilience as a life skill to ensure positive mental health and holistic development amongst adolescents.
2. To explore the role of family in fostering and strengthening resilience amongst adolescents.

2. Literature Review

The word resilience is derived from the Latin word “*resilire*”, meaning to rebound, recoil, or spring back. It is now widely used across multiple fields of study, such as psychology, ecology, engineering, communications, and disaster management. In the context of developmental child psychology, the word resilience refers to ‘resources and processes that promote and protect positive adaptation or development in the context of risk or adversity.’”

According to the American Psychological Association (APA), resilience refers to “the process and outcome of successfully adapting to difficult or challenging life experiences, especially through mental, emotional, and behavioural flexibility and adjustment to external and internal demands.” Several factors contribute to how well people adapt to adversities, among them are:

1. The way in which individuals view and engage with the world,
2. The availability and quality of social resources,
3. Specific coping strategies

As stress is an inevitable part of life, it is essential to cope with such situations effectively, with resilience as a key factor that motivates one to deal with them in a better, healthier way, rather than ignoring the problem or suppressing one’s emotions. Therefore, resilience refers to a person’s ability to adapt and bounce back from unpleasant experiences such as stress, adversity or trauma.

In today’s digital world, adolescents are constantly preoccupied with their positive image on social media platforms, which affects their self-esteem, mindset, emotional regulation, coping ability, relationships with friends and family, and academic performance. As an adolescent evolves through these changes in various areas of their lives, it has been observed that adolescents may develop unhealthy coping mechanisms such as procrastination, withdrawal, excessive screentime, involvement with substance use, self-harm, etc., which impact their overall health. In the current scenario, many adolescents have been found coping with negative experiences by immersing themselves in the world of digital technology, thus overlooking the fact that there is an underlying emotion that they are unable to process, express or cope with.

Another significant experience was COVID-19, which affected the whole world across nationalities, genders, age groups, and ethnicities, highlighting the importance of resilience in the face of adversity. Hence, it is through such experiences that one can build one's coping abilities and become resilient in life, emphasising the crucial role of inculcating life skills among adolescents.

According to WHO, life skills refer to "abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life". 'Adaptive' means that a person is flexible in their approach and able to adjust to different circumstances. 'Positive behaviour' implies that a person is forward-looking and can, even in difficult situations, identify a ray of hope and opportunities for solutions.

Life skills are further divided into three main classifications of skills:

1. Thinking skills such as self-awareness, problem-solving, decision-making, critical thinking, and creative thinking
2. Social skills such as Interpersonal Relationships, Effective Communication, and Empathy
3. Emotional skills such as Managing Feelings/ Emotions, Coping with Stress

Hence, life skills are abilities that promote mental and social well-being and equip young children with the competence to face life's realities. Dr Ginsburg, a child paediatrician and human development expert, proposed seven integral and interrelated components to

inculcate resilience, including competence, confidence, character, contribution, control, and coping.

2.1. Theoretical Framework

The study follows Ecological Systems Theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1994), which emphasises that an individual's development is influenced by multiple systems surrounding and interacting with them. It emphasises the bidirectional influence, i.e., the impact of the setting on a person and the reciprocal influence, i.e. of the person on the environment. He initially proposed an ecological model but later offered a bioecological model, where the former model emphasised contextual influences playing a crucial role in proximal processes in development; the latter model emphasised biology, culture and time, highlighting the interplay between genes and the environment constantly influencing each other in shaping who we become, thus offering a holistic perspective. The following are the five ecological systems:

Microsystem: It refers to the innermost level, i.e. a person's immediate environment, which influences them the most. According to Bronfenbrenner, the microsystem refers to “a pattern of activities, roles and interpersonal relations experienced over time by the developing person in a given setting with particular physical and material characteristics. For example, a child's parents, siblings, grandparents, teachers, classmates and neighbours. It also includes personal characteristics such as temperament, physical attributes, mental abilities and personality. With respect to the influence of the digital world today, both physical and virtual microsystems must be considered essential factors in a child's development.

Mesosystem: It refers to “a system of microsystems”, thus indicating the relationship between different microsystems in an individual's life, such as school and home interaction or between friends and family, etc.

Exosystem: It refers to the environment in which an individual is not an active participant but still impacts their development, such as the parents' workplace, government policies, social services, community resources, and mass media.

Macrosystem: It refers to the broader society and cultural forces that impact an individual's development, such as values, social norms, customs, traditions, ideology and cultural beliefs.

Chronosystem: It refers to the outermost level, where time plays a crucial role in shaping an individual's development, including personal experiences, life transitions, historical events, and societal changes (e.g., the birth of a sibling, parental divorce, or the death of a family member).

Further, the bioecological model emphasises the interplay between the following four key elements:

1. Process (Proximal processes driving development)
2. Person (Individual Characteristics)
3. Context (Environmental Systems)
4. Time (Temporal aspect of development, i.e., individual life and historical)

2.2. Previous Research Findings

In a study by González Moreno & Molero Jurado (2024) on Social skills and creativity as elements that enhance resilience in adolescence, the researchers examined a sample of 743 students aged 14 to 19 years from different educational centres in the province of Almeria (Spain). The researchers used CHASO (i.e., the Social Skills Questionnaire), the Turtle Creativity Questionnaire, and CDRISC-10 (i.e., the Reduced Resilience Scale) to collect the data. This study revealed a positive correlation between resilience and both social skills and creativity, suggesting that developing resilience is crucial to helping adolescents overcome adversity. The study also revealed that boys were more likely to be resilient than girls, suggesting that skills such as assertiveness and independence were more culturally accepted in boys than in girls. No gender differences were found in the creativity domain, indicating that creativity is an intrinsic factor rather than a cultural or socialisation factor, unlike social skills and resilience.

A study conducted by Rani & Neeraj (2020) on 'Life skills of Senior Secondary Students' found a significant difference between adolescent female and male students across all life skills dimensions in the Sonipat district, Haryana. The study was conducted on a sample of 200 female and male students from government and private schools (100 each) using the Life Skill Scale developed by M.N. Vranda (2009). It was revealed that there was a significant difference between adolescent female and male students, where female students were better equipped than male students on the mentioned life skills, such as decision making, problem solving, empathy, self-awareness, coping with emotions, creative thinking and critical thinking; however, there was no significant difference on the dimension of communication skills amongst them.

Another study conducted by Gunawardena, Godamunne, and Chandradasa (2024), on 'The Relationship between Resilience and Mental Health in Adolescents in Non- Western Cultures' revealed four themes fostering resilience amongst adolescents were: family support, physical activity, cultural beliefs and values, gratitude and prosocial behaviours and hence emphasised the need to strengthen such factors at the research, clinical and policy level.

In a study conducted by Antony (2022) on 'Framing Childhood Resilience through Bronfenbrenner Ecological System Theory: A discussion paper', the study stressed the fact that resilience can be cultivated during childhood through personality traits, emotional intelligence at the individual level, effective parenting, secure attachment, effective external support, and school-based interventions to build resilience amongst students. Similarly, Cherian (2024) conducted a study on 'Emotional Regulation, Parenting Style and Resilience amongst Adolescents in Bhopal, India'. The study included students from local schools and coaching institutions, with data collected using self-report measures. The study revealed that authoritative parenting, which is characterised by warmth, support and appropriate levels of control, fosters the development of adaptive emotional regulation strategies and resilience in adolescence. It further revealed that students who struggled with academics, were unable to cope with adversities or challenges in life, were susceptible to negative outcomes such as dropping out, engaging in suicidal behaviour and participating in antisocial activities.

In a study conducted by Feng, Qu, Wang, & Zhang (2024) in China on 'The Impact of Parenting Styles on the Psychological Resilience of Adolescence', emotional warmth and family support were identified as factors that positively correlated with parenting style and psychological resilience. In contrast, factors such as refusal and emotional control were negatively correlated with psychological resilience, emphasising the need for parents to adopt positive parenting methods.

Tare, Verma, and Jahagirdar (2025) did a study 'To Understand the Correlation between Resilience and Positive Mental Health', emphasised that resilience is vital for sustaining both physical and mental wellbeing, as many times our physical concerns or physiological

disruptions such as cardiovascular diseases stems not only from biological condition but also from psychological concerns such as chronic stress or unresolved emotions leading to anxiety and depression and therefore emphasising resilience acting as a protective shield in coping effectively when faced with adversities in life. Thus, it suggests that we can build resilience by ensuring both physical and mental health.

Another study by Kanak and Rangila (2024) examined 'Understanding the Role of Resilience among Adolescents'. The study was conducted on 30 adolescents, 15 girls and 15 boys from Delhi, using semi-structured interviews and the Connor Davidson Scale - 25 to measure resilience. It revealed that resilience played a crucial role in adolescents' lives, positively impacting their academic performance, personal growth, and emotional well-being, as they viewed adversities as opportunities to grow by cultivating a growth mindset and receiving support from others. This study concluded by emphasising the need for parents to navigate adolescence, build resilience, strengthen relationships, promote mental health, prepare for adulthood, foster a supportive environment, and enhance their overall well-being.

A review study by Ungar, Ghazinour, and Richter (2013) titled 'Understanding Resilience within the Social Ecology of Human Development'. The study explored children's interactions with reciprocating systems and the quality of those systems, which impacts developmental success under negative stress. It further stressed the complexity of these interactions, highlighting three guiding principles: first, Equifinality; second, differential impact; and third, contextual and cultural moderation.

2.2.1. Relationship between the Microsystem and Resilience

Campbell-Sill, Cohan, and Stein (2006) conducted a study to understand the 'Relationship between Resilience, Personality and Psychiatric Symptoms in Young Adults', which revealed that resilience was negatively correlated with neuroticism and positively correlated with extraversion and conscientiousness. It further mentioned that task-oriented coping was positively associated with resilience and mediated the relationship between conscientiousness and resilience, whereas emotion-oriented coping was associated with low resilience.

Another study by Ryan, Russell, Huebner, Diaz and Sanchez (2010) on 'Resilience among Family members', identified two main structures of family- firstly, family cohesion and secondly, family adaptability. Family cohesion refers to the emotional bonds among family members and the degree of independence they feel with one another. (for example, emotional attachment, family member involvement). Family Adaptability refers to the capacity to demonstrate flexibility during stressful times in parenting style, problem-solving, beliefs, and values. For example, family reaction to disclosing one's sexual orientation, drug use, suicidal thoughts, etc. Apart from family within the microsystem, peers, teachers, and the school also contribute to an individual's development, and the more an individual feels connected, accepted, and supported, the more likely they are to exhibit prosocial behaviour. Further, resilience was found among youth who were engaged in religious institutions.

A study conducted by Kumari (2025) on 'The Role of Resilience in Adolescents' Psychological Development' emphasised the significant role of support from family, positive peer relationships, community, and the educational environment, as well as individual characteristics (such as self-esteem, problem-solving skills, emotional regulation, and coping mechanisms). It also stressed the role of cultural beliefs, values, and social norms in shaping an individual's resilience. The study mentioned efforts by educational, community-based organisations and governments in Finland, Canada, and Australia to build resilience amongst adolescents. Hence, this study emphasised resilience as a significant factor in adolescent psychological development.

3. Methodology

This study explores the role resilience plays in an individual's holistic development and how families can foster resilience among adolescents by analysing secondary data from academic articles, psychological studies, and case reports.

4. Discussion

Based on a review of the literature and analyses of academic articles, psychological studies, and case reports, this study emphasises that resilience plays a significant role in promoting positive mental health and ensuring the holistic development of adolescents. Positive correlations were found between resilience and social skills, creativity, and adaptive coping strategies, as well as traits such as extraversion and conscientiousness. In contrast, a negative association was observed with neuroticism and maladaptive emotional coping (González Moreno & Molero Jurado, 2024).

With respect to gender, boys reported higher levels of resilience, indicating the sociocultural reinforcement of assertiveness and independence, though there was no significant gender difference in the creativity domain (Cherian, 2024). It was emphasised that females demonstrated strong abilities in various life skills, such as decision-making, problem-solving, empathy, self-awareness, emotion regulation, creative and critical thinking, with no gender differences in communication skills (Rani & Neeraj, 2020).

Studies further reiterated the crucial role of family in inculcating resilience among adolescents. In terms of parenting styles, the authoritative parenting style, characterised by warmth, support, and appropriate levels of control and discipline, fosters the development of adaptive emotion regulation strategies and is positively associated with psychological resilience. In contrast, rejection, excessive emotional control, and an unhealthy family environment were negatively correlated. Adolescents who were unable to cope with adversities or challenges in life were found to be susceptible to negative outcomes such as academic failure, dropout, engaging in maladaptive behaviour and may be exposed to mental health concerns. Thus, highlighting the importance of a positive family environment and support in strengthening self-esteem and sense of worth, and in inculcating resilience. Many studies have reiterated the crucial role of family cohesion and adaptability in strengthening resilience among adolescents.

In addition, positive relationships with peers, teachers, and the school, along with regular physical activity, values, cultural beliefs, gratitude (Gunawardena, Godamunne, and Chandradasa 2024), participation in religious activities, and prosocial behaviour were identified as significant factors contributing to resilience among adolescents. Further, studies have revealed that resilience was associated with high self-esteem, life satisfaction, academic achievement, and reduced levels of anxiety and depression, thus reiterating the positive relationship between resilience and positive mental health. Thus, the current study emphasises resilience as a protective mechanism to ensure positive mental health and holistic well-being in adolescents when faced with adversity.

5. Conclusions

The findings of this study highlight the significant role of resilience in promoting positive mental health and holistic well-being among adolescents. Within the Bronfenbrenner ecological system, the family within the microsystem plays a vital role in fostering resilience among adolescents, with certain individual and environmental factors making significant

contributions. Individual factors such as one's traits, temperament, physical attributes, mental ability, emotional intelligence, and environmental factors such as secure attachments, authoritative parenting, family cohesion and adaptability, warmth in the family, along with positive relationships with peers, teachers and school, strengthen resilience at the micro level. Thus, it is imperative to inculcate adolescents with essential life skills - particularly resilience- to help them effectively navigate challenges across all domains such as social-emotional, physical and psychological. In conclusion, resilience fosters socio-emotional competence and psychological stability, serving as a vital protective factor that supports healthy adolescent development and overall well-being.

6. Suggestions to foster resilience in adolescents

Hence, the following are key factors that can foster resilience among adolescents :

1. Providing a safe and secure attachment with the parent
2. Encourage open communication and healthy expression of emotions
3. Modelling healthy coping skills by parents, as children learn more through observation
4. Teaching and practising emotional regulation and stress management techniques
5. Letting them experience manageable failures or rejections in life and reflect upon their learning
6. Support from parents, peers and teachers
7. By setting realistic goals
8. Accepting change as a part of life
9. Providing them with an opportunity for problem-solving
10. Providing them opportunities to support others
11. Inculcating an optimistic or growth mindset
12. Practising mindfulness regularly
13. Encouraging regular physical activity
14. Practising self-care regularly

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